

Digitalization of Education and Entrepreneurship Development in Enugu State

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The study evaluated the Digitalization of education and Entrepreneurship development in Enugu State. The specific objectives of the study were to: examine the relationship between online course creators and easy access to consumers and ascertain the relationship between Captivating digital content and potential market growth. The area of the study was Enugu state. Institutions that make use of online programs were selected for the study. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. A total population of Two hundred and thirty-three (233) staff as used. Two hundred and six (206) staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. Data was presented and analyzed using Likert Scale and the hypotheses using Pearson correlation coefficient (r). The findings indicated that online course creators had positive significant relationship with easy access to consumers as reported in the probability value of ($r = .396 < 750, p < .05$) and Captivating digital content had positive significant relationship with potential market growth as reported in the probability value of ($r = .433 < 712, p < .05$). The study concluded that online course creators and Captivating digital content had positive significant relationship with easy access to consumers and potential market growth. The study recommended among others that the institutions should try and create and launch online courses, to gain a better understanding of the target audience.

ABSTRACT

Keywords: Digitalization of Education; Entrepreneurship Development; Consumer and Potential Market; Enugu State

Introduction

Technological developments in the 21st century have transformed most of the creation of wealth from the physical form into knowledge-based. Technology and knowledge are core factors in production. With the increased mobility of information and the global workforce, knowledge and expertise can be instantly transmitted worldwide, and any advantage gained by a company can be eliminated through competitive upgrades overnight. The only comparative advantage a company will enjoy will be its innovation process by combining market know-how and technology with the creative talents of knowledge workers to resolve a steady stream of competitive issues and its ability to gains value from information in the knowledge-based economy and knowledge management in the new information society (Montealegre and Cascio, 2016). Digitalization of business processes as a fundamental element of innovative business management leads to a qualitative transformation of the business paradigm of an individual enterprise and the modernization of entire sectors of the economy or the entire economic system. Digital transformation impacts businesses by improving the efficiency of their operations, enabling large-scale automation. Naturally, there are fewer human errors which directly leads to a decrease in operational costs. Entrepreneurship education, the process of knowledge, skill, competency, and attitude development, aims to maximize the effectiveness of the entrepreneurial capacity building. The pandemic boosted the digital transformation of higher education and brought the online incubation platform NETMIB to life, (Toth-Pajor, Bedo & Csapi, (2023), To ensure existence, education firms must innovate to stay ahead of the competition by offering new goods or services, improving their learning processes and organizational structures, or enhancing the marketing of their operations. In the context of education, how may innovation bring value? To begin with, education innovations have the potential to increase learning outcomes and educational quality. Changes in the educational system or teaching techniques might aid in customizing the educational experience. The use of ICT and innovative ways of managing schools are central to emerging trends in customized learning. Secondly, learning is viewed as a method of improving equity and equality in most countries. Innovations might assist increased services to and usage of education and also learning results equally. Lastly, education must stay relevant in the face of fast societal and economic changes (Pange, Lekka, and Toki,2010). Online platforms for lectures, assignments, and exams have become the norm, and digital tools like video conferencing, collaborative software, and learning management systems have become essential. The pandemic has highlighted the importance of digital readiness and has pushed HEIs to invest in technology and training to support their students and faculty better. With the rise of the digital economy, it is essential for HEIs to prepare their students for the demands of entrepreneurship in this field (Ratten & Usmanij,2021). This can involve providing students with a strong digital literacy and technology foundation and offering courses and programs focusing on innovation, creativity, and business acumen (Haleem, Javaid, Qadri, & Suman, 2022). Based on this, the study aimed at evaluating the Digitalization of education and Entrepreneurship development in Enugu state.

Statement of the Problem

Opportunities for entrepreneurs, as well as, for creative destruction, are becoming greater in the digital economy. The application of new technology enables entrepreneurs to offer new digital solutions that can change the world radically. The business creativity and innovations, involved in entrepreneurial activity, as well as, resulting learning process, speed up the discovery of the dominant design for product-market combinations, enable knowledge spillovers, increase productivity, and stimulate economic growth. The availability of different service channels like institutions websites, social media, online advertising as well as various consumer purchasing devices such as smartphones, laptops and tablets has intensified challenges for Institutions. In addition, challenges of online course creators and captivating digital content are not left out. Today, educational goals increasingly encompass new ideas such as the liberation of learners, skills needed for modern society, empathy, and complex vocational skills. As a result of these, it will lead to poor access to consumers, reduced potential market growth, lack of entrepreneurial knowledge, lack of skills, and entrepreneurial attitudes, if not tackled. Based on this, the study aimed at Digitalization of education and Entrepreneurship development in Enugu state.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to evaluate Digitalization of education and Entrepreneurship development in Enugu state. The specific objectives of the study were to:

- i. Examine the relationship between online course creators and easy access to consumers
- ii. Ascertain the relationship between Captivating digital content and potential market growth

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

- i. What is the relationship between online course creators and easy access to consumers?
- ii. What is the relationship between Captivating digital content and potential market growth?

Statement of the Hypotheses

The following Hypotheses guided the study

- i. Online course creators have significant relationship with the easy access to consumers.
- ii. Captivating digital content has significant relationship with potential market growth.

Significance of the Study

It is anticipated that the findings of the study will pave way for the sustainable economy in Nigeria to accept the variable that affects entrepreneurship and business development. Such an acceptance could be utilized to improve on the digitalization of education. The outcome of this study would enable the researcher to understand better the Digitalization of education practices through entrepreneurship and business development.

Review of the Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Digitalization

Teaching is a profession, which is on its way to becoming revolutionized by the use of new technologies. The use of technology in the classroom can help teachers and students achieve better results. Digitization is the process of converting information into a digital (i.e., computer-readable) format. The result is the representation of an object, image, sound, document, or signal (usually an analog signal) obtained by generating a series of numbers that describe a discrete set of points or samples (Mirzagayeva, & Aslanov, 2022). Digitization is of crucial importance to data processing, storage, and transmission, because it "allows information of all kinds in all formats to be carried with the same efficiency and also intermingled". In digital education, students can easily access recorded lectures and use them as a reference. This helps them understand the subject better and speed up the entire learning process. It is also very convenient to access additional reading materials and other learning sources.

Education

Education is fundamental to development and growth. Education is a discipline that is concerned with methods of teaching and learning in schools or school-like environments as opposed to various nonformal and informal means of socialization (Bowen, Mukerji and Lauwerys, 2023). The human mind makes possible all development achievements, from health advances and agricultural innovations to efficient public administration and private sector growth. Education is a purposeful activity directed at achieving certain aims, such as transmitting knowledge or fostering skills and character traits. These aims may include the development of understanding, rationality, kindness, and honesty. Today, educational goals increasingly encompass new ideas such as the liberation of learners, skills needed for modern society, empathy, and complex vocational skills (Rabbni, 2023). Education socializes children into society by teaching cultural values and norms. It equips them with the skills needed to become

productive members of society. This way, it stimulates economic growth and raises awareness of local and global problems.

Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship is the creation or extraction of economic value. It is viewed as change, generally entailing risk beyond what is normally encountered in starting a business, which may include other values than simply economic ones. Byju's, (2023) defined entrepreneurship as the ability and readiness to develop, organize and run a business enterprise, along with any of its uncertainties in order to make a profit. The entrepreneur is defined as someone who has the ability and desire to establish, administer and succeed in a startup venture along with risk entitled to it, to make profits. Entrepreneurship is also one of the resources economists categorize as integral to production, the other three being land/natural resources, labor, and capital. In a broader sense, entrepreneurship is the process of transforming the status quo by solving the most pressing problems and pain points in our society, often by introducing an innovative product or service or creating new markets (Shopify, 2023).

Digitalization of Education Through Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship education is one of the knowledge transfer processes in creating entrepreneurs. The digital transformation in entrepreneurship education is a new approach and an important challenge in education to prepare students in the face of technological change. Currently, building a technology-based entrepreneurship education curriculum is critical, whereby the digitalization process can expand student partnerships and networks with their peers across countries, entrepreneurial educators, and the business communities (Permatasari, & Anggadwita, 2019). *Digitization is the integration of digital technologies into everyday life by the digitization of everything that can be digitized. Entrepreneurship education strategies based on local wisdom and assistance in adopting digital technology will be able to reduce unemployment and increase entrepreneurial creativity of the nation's children to compete and face the world of work. But in its development, a good collaboration is needed between support from government policies, teaching staff, and high interest and motivation from students to make it happen* (Rohaetin, 2020).

Online Course Creators

Online courses and education are widely gaining popularity due to providing unlimited opportunities for students. With e-learning, students can choose courses based on their interests, learn at a safe pace, and still earn certificates acknowledging their skills & expertise. An online course creator is a person that creates online courses (mostly in pre-recorded format) and shares their expertise with students worldwide, alongside monetizing their knowledge (Gevorhyan, 2022). These individuals do not necessarily have teaching certification or education. However, they have expertise in certain areas and are able to share reliable knowledge. Online course creators succeed by understanding their target audience's needs and creating valuable, high-quality content that meets those needs. (Gevorhyan, 2022) noted that the main steps you will go through as an online course creator include doing research for the market and the audience, planning and structuring your course, choosing a platform, and starting marketing for sales. Each of these steps has a vital part in your overall success.

Captivating Digital Content

Captivating Digital Content shows the audience who you are and what you believe. To be successful, every business has to tell its stories. These days, such stories are usually told through posting content online in blogs, articles and social media. But just pushing content onto the web is meaningless if it does not interest the audience. In an online world bursting with billions and billions of pages of content, with new content being added every minute - how do you ensure you are creating compelling content that generates views? Whether it is defining the details that will capture interest, timing the posts to grab the most views or choosing the right venue for the message, there are strategies that will help the online voice be heard, (Expert Panel, 2018). If there is one aspect of digital marketing that is important to get right, content is often one of the first things that spring to mind. Without good content, what do we really have? It is the solid foundation upon which everything else within our marketing strategies is built, (Lynch, 2018).

Business

Business is an economic activity that involves the exchange, purchase, sale or production of goods and services with a motive to earn profits and satisfy the needs of customers. Businesses can be either profit or non-profit organizations that function to gain profits or achieve a social cause respectively. It is not concerned with the achievement of social and emotional objectives. Every business activity includes an exchange or transfer of services and goods to earn value (Byju's, 2022). Good business describes companies that have broadened the definition of success beyond the bottom line to include the impact the organization has on all constituents, their communities, and even the world. In other words, it is an outward focus. *Business* is a usually commercial or mercantile activity engaged in as a means of livelihood. Businesses range in scale and scope from sole proprietorships to large, international corporations (Hayes, Ames & Kazel, 2023).

Development

Development refers to activities leading to the acquisition of new knowledge or skills for purposes of growing. Development is visible and useful, not necessarily immediately, and includes an aspect of quality change and the creation of conditions for a continuation of that change (SID, 2021). Development is basically an economic concept that has positive connotations; it involves the application of certain economic and technical measures to utilize available resources to instigate economic growth and improve people's quality of life. Development is designed to improve the quality and performance of present managers and provide growth for present as well as future requirements and need (Majeed and Shakeel, 2017).

Business Development

Business development entails tasks and processes to develop and implement growth opportunities within and between organizations. Business development can be summarized as the ideas, initiatives, and activities that help make a business better. This includes increasing revenues, growth in terms of business expansion, increasing profitability by building strategic partnerships, and making strategic business decisions (Seth, James and Li, 2022). Successful business development impacts every department within an organization including sales, marketing, manufacturing, human resources, accounting, finance, product development, and vendor management. Business development is to be thought of as a marketing tactic. The objectives include branding, expansion in markets, new user acquisition, and awareness. However, the main function of business development is to utilize partners in selling to the right customers. Creating opportunities for value to be ongoing in the long term is important. To be successful in business development the partnership must be built on strong relationships. Business development, also known as biz dev, encapsulates a combination of sales, marketing, and networking activities that add value to the brand (Heaslip 2022).

Potential Market Growth

A potential market is crucial *when a company expands its product line or customer base*. Market growth is the change in the size of a market or industry. It can be an increase, or decrease, on either a quantitative, or qualitative level. This can be done through the introduction of new products and services, and by increasing demand for those products or services (Williams and Hawks, 2022). A potential market is a part of the market that can capture in the future. It includes the demographic groups that are not customers. Market research plays an important role in the process of understanding potential markets. The size of a potential market helps to understand the level of investment that should be made in the market (Tharwani, 2022). If the potential market is small, it means a small fraction of the total population is showing interest in the available product. However, if the size of the potential market is large, it means a huge fraction of the total population is showing interest in the product or category.

Conceptual Framework of the Study

Fig 1 Conceptual framework of the study

Source: Researcher, 2023

Theoretical Framework

The Joseph Schumpeter's Theory of entrepreneurship guided the study:

Joseph Schumpeter's Theory of entrepreneurship was developed in the year 1942. G.F. Papanek (1962) and J.R. Harris (1970)

Joseph Schumpeter's theory of entrepreneurship was developed in the year 1942. G.F. Papanek (1962) and J.R. Harris (1970) concluded that entrepreneurship is an important factor that influences entrepreneurial activity. Economic gains spontaneously develop the desire to pursue diverse entrepreneurial ventures among entrepreneurs. The relationship between a person's intrinsic motivation and desired economic gains has a profound influence on the development of entrepreneurial skills. Whenever certain economic conditions are favorable, entrepreneurial growth and economic growth take place. Entrepreneurial incentives are a major motivator for entrepreneurial activities. Speaking of innovations, he noted the new combination of factors of production, Schumpeter gave the entrepreneur the role of innovator, who was not just an ordinary executive, but an innovator (Daniel and David, 2021). Schumpeter starts with the assumption of a purely competitive economy in a stationary state. In such an economy, there is no uncertainty, no economic profit, stable money supply, stable income velocity of money, stable price level, and no economic growth.

Empirical Review

The relationship between online course creators and easy access to consumers

Li, Nishimura, Yagami and Park (2021) carried out a study on an Empirical Study on Online Learners' Continuance Intentions in China. Online education in China is developing at a rapid pace due to its unique advantages, and its sustainable development is becoming increasingly crucial. Thus, this study attempted to understand learners' continuance intentions in an online learning environment and examined the factors influencing online learners' continuous retention. The research model for the influencing factors and study hypotheses were constructed based on multiple theoretical and synthesized perspectives, such as the information system success model; interactions between students, content, and instructors; and the theory of perceived value. To achieve the stated objectives, we conducted a questionnaire survey, in which 382 valid responses were collected from Chinese respondents from 32 provinces in China in April and May 2020. Furthermore, this study primarily employed Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) and Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) to test the constructed model. The results indicate that service quality, course quality, and student-instructor interaction have indirect and positive effects on learners' continuance intentions for online learning, while the variable of perceived value is a significant mediator for online learners' retention and has a direct influence on their continuance intentions. Student-student interaction and student-content interaction does not have direct or indirect effects on online learners' continuance intentions.

Yuan, Donghong, Lidong, Xiaodong and Shengliang (2021) conducted a study on Understanding consumers' purchase intention towards online paid courses. With the unprecedented development of information and communication technologies, online learning is increasingly seen as an important channel for knowledge acquisition. Although knowledge payment platforms have attracted a considerable number of consumers, little is known about the determinants of purchase intention of online learning consumers for online paid courses (OPCs). In this study, we identify the mechanism underlying online learning consumers' purchase intentions towards online paid courses (OPCs) based on outcome expectation and trust. We further examine the antecedents of performance expectation and trust from a learning-oriented perspective. Results indicate that trust and performance expectation play positive roles in consumer purchase intention. Moreover, perceived lecturer expertise, prior learning experience, and personal trial experience are positively associated with trust and performance expectation, which in turn influence purchase intention towards OPCs. The data were collected using a questionnaire survey of 443 users of knowledge payment platforms, and the proposed model was analysed through structural equation modelling. This study enhances the theoretical understanding of why consumers purchase OPCs in the knowledge payment context. For information system practice, these findings provide new insights for managers on how to conduct knowledge product transactions effectively.

Andreas and Bohrs (2022) carried out a study on the Experiences and Future Expectations towards Online Courses: An Empirical Study of the B2C-and B2B-Segments This article explores the future potential for the development of online courses. The findings are based on an empirical study with 3 sample groups: (1) B2C segment in Germany, (2) B2C segment in the United States, and (3) B2B segment (international). In the first step the status quo of the use of e-learning in general and online courses in particular is presented. Subsequently, the expectations of potential users concerning the design of online courses are determined. Respondents were segmented according to their basic needs, based on ten distinct attributes relevant for the decision-making process. Thirdly, an innovative concept for online courses is reviewed as part of a concept test. Since people increasingly watch (short) videos instead of reading documents, the authors emphasize that creators of online courses can take advantage of this development, provided they adapt their formats to the changed communication behavior of potential users.

Lan, Saeed and Khong (2022) carried out a study on the Factors drive the purchase of paid online courses A systematic literature review. Despite a surge of empirical work on paid Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), a review of factors that drive the sales of them remains unexplored. The study aims to consolidate the existing fragmented knowledge by synthesizing the current literature on quality attributes, methodological approaches, theoretical foundations, and additional research opportunities for future studies on sales of MOOCs. Through an extensive literature search in Scopus and Web of Science, we evaluated 12 peer-reviewed articles across years. The results indicate that (1) most studies adopted quantitative approaches relied on online surveys or web crawling of platform databases, (2) there were three main groups of theoretical bases adopted, (3) quality attributes on courses, instructors and platforms were vital in influencing consumers' purchasing behaviors and (4) however, their weights might vary based on their platform availability and visibility. This paper contributes to spur awareness and interest in continued research towards the sales of paid online courses and serves as a reference source for higher education (HE) practitioners to improve the quality of their online courses to meet the demands of consumers.

Pallavi, Ramachandran and Chinnasamy (2022) An Empirical Study on Effectiveness of E-Learning Over Conventional Class Room Learning – A Case Study with Respect to Online Degree Programme in Higher Education. Learning and teaching domains are going on major higher education companies of e-learning Ideas and practices changes due to quick acceptance. Many universities all over the world are now beginning to offer Internet-based courses that complement classroom-based courses. Online courses offer learners various such as benefits facilities, Teachers, and other close to students to serve flexibility and opportunities from various schools or around the world. The education system and mode of education are changing over the period of time. In instructional technology Innovations often are implemented in traditional ways. TV significantly changes the way people learn, and it stays that way Existing instruction by providing a speaking head as an instructional tool built into the paradigm for sending information to students. Active learning, Cooperative learning, Project-based teaching and despite such educational innovations contextual face-to-face instruction in learning changed character, online courses tend to develop more traditional concepts Learning. Mostly an online course's primary objective is to transfer information from the instructor to the student accessing information to students and expecting them to Prove their learning in an exam. The development

of online instruction programs for online course developers raises an interesting question. Online study designers follow the traditional methods or incorporate online programs' innovative approaches. Primary factors behind the use of online learning improve the quality of education, and also improve the cost-effectiveness of education by reducing costs. Face-to-face Online learning is used successfully with positive effects on career and education. A geographically distributed team within an organization can simultaneously train their skills through online sites and gain greater Competitiveness. Online learning can be beneficial because Students at their own pace can learn through online products. Virtual classrooms are available anywhere with an Internet connection, take advantage of this great way to travel. Gurukul's system of education changed to imparting knowledge in a classroom setting followed by hybrid learning and at present, one new way of learning has emerged as a full-fledged mode to earn a degree i.e., online learning. Online learning comprises of both hybrid/ bended learning (comprises traditional face-to face classes, learning over the internet and learning supported by other technologies) and purely online learning is competing for course delivery through the internet. Due to its flexible and user-friendly features, online learning has been gaining attention from learners and education institutions. Learning is self-phased and effectiveness of learning is achieved if it fulfills the learners' expectation in imparting knowledge, uninterrupted support from the instructor whenever needed, disbursement of the learning materials, communication, and motivation. The objectives of this paper are to study the effectiveness of e-learning compared to conventional classroom learning. The study also shows that a major portion of learners cannot set time for study, homework, and assignments completion. The institutions along with the routine learning can also include sessions for motivation, a sense of accountability, and responsibility which may enhance discipline among learners. A significant portion of learners feels that online learning will not enhance the sense of belongingness. The institutions can create provisions at the campus for the e-learners to meet up occasionally for the interaction between learners and faculties. A portion of E-learners feels that the learning material in e-learning is not effective as that of conventional mode.

The Relationship Between Captivating Digital Contact and Potential Market Growth

Hailiang, Prabuddha and Yu (2013) carried out a study on IT-Enabled Broadcasting in social media: An Empirical Study of Artists' Activities and Music Sales. With the emergence of social media and Web 2.0, broadcasting in the online environment has evolved into a new form of marketing due to the much broader reach enabled by information technology. This paper quantifies the effect of artists' different broadcasting activities on a leading social media site for music, MySpace, on music sales. We employ a panel vector auto-regression (PVAR) model to investigate the inter-relationship between broadcasting promotions in social media and music sales, while controlling for influential factors such as album prices, advertising in traditional media channels, artist popularity, and the impact of user-generated content. We characterize two types of broadcast messages under the MySpace context, personal and automated. We find that broadcasting in social media has a significant effect on sales even after controlling for the aforementioned factors, and more importantly the effect mainly comes from personal messages rather than automated messages. Our findings also point to the importance of conducting captivating conversations with customers in the organizational use of social media.

Owusu-Kyei, Kong, Akomeah & Afriyie (2022) conducted a study on the Impact of Digital Marketing Communication on Organizational Growth. This paper offers views on some current and future trends in marketing. The content is based on recent literature and on what is happening in the business world. The study explains digital marketing communication and its impact on organizational growth. It is known in today's marketing world that; digital medium of communication has become new norm for most organizations. It is important to note that social media space has huge audience therefore it is right to target from the various social media platforms. The study examines digital communication medium like visual advertising, social media (Facebook, Instagram and WhatsApp), E-mail and also website. The target population was 200 clients of Kelondo, however the sample size of 200 was determined by using Muller and Brewer (2003) formula: $n = P / (1 + P (\delta)^2)$. Therefore, the size was 193. The questionnaire used for this research consisted of only closed – ended questions. The survey was created using Google forms online platform and distributed randomly through social media platforms like WhatsApp, and personal contacts. The online survey contained multiple choices which allow respondents to express themselves by selecting the best possible answers to the questions asked. This enabled us to collect and analyze accurate information collected. The quantitative data collected through the questionnaire was coded in Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) a tool for data analysis. I then went forward to analyze the data and the answers were then available in tables and chart.

Pollák and Markovič (2021) carried out a study on the Size of Business Unit as a Factor Influencing Adoption of Digital Marketing: Empirical Analysis of SMEs Operating in the Central European Market. The issue of using marketing communication tools in the internet environment is quite extensive. Innovation of the usual procedures is usually influenced by market development. The presented study examines selected factors that may affect the acceptance of digital marketing tools in business practice in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). The aim of the study is to answer the basic question of whether company size influences the willingness to adopt online marketing tools within the usual communication mix. Based on a thorough empirical analysis performed on a sample of companies operating in the Central European market, it can be stated that company size does not play a role in adopting online marketing tools. Most organizations, regardless of their size, still have reservations about investing in digital marketing. On the other hand, previous experience is a key determinant to perceive the benefits of using the internet for business purposes. Organizations actively using online marketing tools evaluate their contribution to their business very positively. It is a well-known fact that product testing significantly increases the degree of its acceptance. This knowledge is one of the key starting points in traditional marketing. Obviously, this assumption needs to be taken into account in both physical and digital environments. At the same time, it should be noted that the application of the basic online marketing tools in business practice is a prerequisite for all subsequent online activities.

Allam and Zalafa (2022) conducted a study on the E-Marketing and Its Strategies: Digital Opportunities and Challenges. The current article deals with the topic of e-marketing, its strategies, opportunities and digital challenges, as one of the most successful and capable mechanisms that can reach as many customers as possible. It also examines the basic concepts of e-marketing, its features, multiple stages, multiple mechanisms, the reasons for its spread, and its pros and cons. The study relied on the descriptive approach. The most important findings of the research were: the application of e-marketing requires the provision of the appropriate digital environment, the availability of the Internet and the proliferation of e-management have made e-marketing a necessity of our era, and the success of e-marketing requires relying on accurate strategies carefully studied. The research has also indicated that several strategies can be used in the same organization in accordance with the development of the internal and external environment of the organization, and that there is no better strategy than the other. Rather, the nature of the environment and the objectives set out make the organization resort to strategies at the expense of the other, and the successful choice from the various strategies should be based on studies and analytical research of various inputs and outputs of information as well as the accuracy and actual ability of objectives to be reflected. The research also clarified that the use of e-marketing strategies provides many opportunities, such as achieving a competitive advantage and a strategic position in the market. Furthermore, it has shown that although the e-marketing strategy is effective, there are still many challenges that require intensified efforts to counter the negative effects of establishing confidence in customers and encouraging them to seek their services and instilling a culture of digital communication.

Idongesit, Eshiett and Uwhubetine (2022) conducted a study on Digital Content Marketing and Customer Loyalty in Nigerian University. The evolution of marketing concepts in recent years has made possible the use of various contents that are perceptible, comprehensible, and appreciable by customers. Such avenues are tailored to suit the needs and expectations of the customers in the digital era of content marketing in business. In essence, business concerns could aspire to design a dependable platform using engaging content to attract customers by satisfying and retaining them for future business growth and development. The purpose of this study is to examine the effect of digital content marketing in directing traffic to a particular content owner through an increased level of customer loyalty. The study defines and appraises the concept of digital content marketing and the effect of engaging marketing content on customer loyalty. The respondents for this study were postgraduate students of Ahmadu Bello University, Nigeria. The study designed and administered some digital Content marketing-related questions that could induce customer loyalty to respondents. The data obtained from the study were analyzed using the Pearson Correlation Coefficient technique; the study revealed that the accomplishment of unambiguous and dependable content by business concerns could increase the delight of organizational customers. The analysis of data revealed that there is a link between digital content marketing and customer loyalty in Nigerian Universities. In conclusion, the study appraises the need for effective dissemination of information through digital marketing content to encourage end-users to break away from the grip of traditional marketing platforms and embrace the new concept of digital content marketing in Nigeria.

Gap in Empirical Review

The studies done were carried outside Digitalization of education through Entrepreneurship and Business development for sustainable Economy and did not focus to best of my knowledge on the online course creators and easy access to consumers; digital retailers and potential market growth of the selected institutions understudy. Most of the studies reviewed analyzed their data through A purposeful sampling technique, Descriptive statistics and appropriate inferential statistics, Purposive Sampling technique, Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient, Multiple sampling technique, Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) method, Simple linear regression and Z test while the present study made use of Pearson correlation coefficient (r) to test the hypotheses. Therefore, the study aimed at filling this research gap by evaluating the Digitalization of education through Entrepreneurship and Business development for sustainable Economy.

Methodology

The area of the study was Enugu Enugu state, on the Digitalization of education through Entrepreneurship development in Enugu state. Two hundred and thirty-three (233) staff of the institutions that make online programs was utilized were selected for the study. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. Two hundred and six (206) staff returned their questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 88 percent response rate. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.74 which was also good. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score (3.0 and above agreed while below 3.0 disagreed) and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Pearson correlation (r) test statistic tool.

Data Presentation and Analyses

Relationship between online course creators and easy access to consumers

Table 2: Responses to research question one on the relationship between online course creators and easy access to consumers

		5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 DA	1 SD	ΣFX	- X	SD	Decision
1	More people turn to online learning for its flexibility	360	192	48	58	41	699	3.39	1.557	Agree
		72	48	16	29	41	206			
		35.0	23.3	7.8	14.1	19.9	100%			
2	Online course promotes ability to advance a career	245	192	75	36	66	614	2.98	1.602	Agree
		49	48	25	18	66	206			
		23.8	23.3	12.1	8.7	32.0	100%			
3	Virtual collaboration opportunities are enhanced through online	335	212	78	40	40	705	3.42	1.505	Agree
		67	53	26	20	40	206			
		32.5	25.7	12.6	9.7	19.4	100%			
4	The online courses give the chance to spend time with work	405	180	21	84	31	721	3.50	1.536	Agree
		81	45	7	42	31	206			
		39.3	21.8	3.4	20.4	15.0	100%			
5	A broader range of perspectives are observed	375	180	54	40	48	697	3.38	1.603	Agree
		75	45	18	20	48	206			
		36.4	21.8	8.7	9.7	23.3	100%			
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.334	1.5606	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 2, 120 respondents out of 206 representing 58.3 percent agreed that more people turn to online learning for its flexibility with mean score 3.39 and a standard deviation of 1.557. Online course promotes ability to advance a career 97 respondents representing 47.1 percent agreed with a mean score of 2.98 and a standard deviation of 1.602. Virtual collaboration opportunities are enhanced through online 120 respondents representing 58.2 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.42 and standard deviation of 1.505. The online courses give the chance to spend time with work 126 respondents representing 61.1 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.50 and 1.536. A broader range of perspectives are observed 120 respondents representing 58.2 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.38 and a standard deviation of 1.603.

Relationship Between Captivating Digital Content and Potential Market Growth

Table 3: Responses to Research Question Two on The Relationship Between Captivating Digital Content and Potential Market Growth

		5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 DA	1 SD	ΣFX	- X	SD	Decision
1	The e-learning has improved knowing the audience first and foremost	395	244	21	88	15	763	3.7	1.360	Agree
		79	61	7	44	15	206	0		
		38.3	29.6	3.4	21.4	7.3	100%			
2	The connecting with the audience through digitalization has enhanced the business growth in the society	300	244	3	76	46	669	3.2	1.578	Agree
		60	61	1	38	46	206	5		
		29.1	29.6	.5	18.4	22.3	100%			
3	Digitalization aids in providing Interesting educational material that helps audience to do things they want to do	340	252	18	80	29	719	3.4	1.468	Agree
		68	63	6	40	29	206	9		
		33.0	30.6	2.9	19.4	14.1	100%			
4	There is accessing of broader target market with digital transformation	320	204	69	21	62	676	3.2	1.637	Agree
		64	51	23	6	62	206	4		
		31.1	24.8	11.2	2.9	30.1	100%			
5	Delivering value on a consistent basis as a result of digitalization	405	160	42	86	28	721	3.5	1.510	Agree
		81	40	14	43	28	206	0		
		39.3	19.4	6.8	20.9	13.6	100%			
	Total Grand mean and standard deviation							3.43	1.5106	
								6		

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 3, 140 respondents out of 206 representing 67.9 percent agreed that the e-learning has improved knowing the audience first and foremost with mean score 3.70 and a standard deviation of 1.360. The connecting with the audience through digitalization has enhanced the business growth in the society 121 respondents representing 58.7 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.25 and a standard deviation of 1.578. Digitalization aids in providing Interesting educational material that helps audience to do things they want to do 131 respondents representing 63.6 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.49 and standard deviation of 1.468. There is accessing of broader target market with digital transformation 115 respondents representing 55.9 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.24 and 1.637. Delivering value on a consistent basis as a result of digitalization 121 respondents representing 58.7 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.50 and a standard deviation of 1.510.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypotheses one: Online Course Creators Has Relationship with Easy Access to Consumers

Table 4: Shows Pearson Correlation on Online Course Creators Has Relationship with Easy Access to Consumers

Table 4: Correlations						
		More people turn to online learning for its flexibility	Online course promotes ability to advance a career	Virtual collaboration opportunities are enhanced through online	The online courses give the chance to spend time with work	A broader range of perspectives are observed
More people turn to online learning for its flexibility	Pearson Correlation	1	.629**	.637**	.546**	.561**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	206	206	206	206	206
Online course promotes ability to advance a career	Pearson Correlation	.629**	1	.538**	.409**	.396**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	206	206	206	206	206
Virtual collaboration opportunities are enhanced through online	Pearson Correlation	.637**	.538**	1	.544**	.750**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	206	206	206	206	206
The online courses gives the chance to spend time with work	Pearson Correlation	.546**	.409**	.544**	1	.621**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	206	206	206	206	206
A broader ranger of perspectives ae observed	Pearson Correlation	.561**	.396**	.750**	.621**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	206	206	206	206	206

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4, is the Pearson correlation matrix on online course creators and easy access to consumers showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows .396 < 750. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 levels (2 tailed) and implies that online course creators had positive significant relationship with easy access to consumers (r=.396 < 750). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of r = .195 with 879 degrees of freedom at alpha level for a two-tailed test (r.396 < 750, p>.05).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise reject the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed $r = .396 < 750$ is greater than the table value of $.195$, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we conclude that online course creators had positive significant relationship with easy access to consumers as reported in the probability value of $(r = .396 < 750, p > .05)$.

Hypotheses two: Captivating Digital Content Has Relationship with Potential Market Growth

Table 5: Shows Pearson Correlation on Captivating Digital Content Have Relationship with Potential Market Growth

Table 5: Correlations						
		The e-learning has improved knowing the audience first and foremost	The connecting with the audience through digitalization enhanced the business growth in the society	Digitalization aids in providing Interesting educational material that helps audience to do things they want to do	There is accessing of broader target market with digital transformation.	Delivering value on a consistent basis as a result of digitalization
The e-learning has improved knowing the audience first and foremost	Pearson Correlation	1	.703**	.701**	.558**	.567**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	206	206	206	206	206
The connecting with the audience through digitalization enhanced the business growth in the society	Pearson Correlation	.703**	1	.712**	.546**	.556**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	206	206	206	206	206
Digitalization aids in providing Interesting educational material that helps audience to do things they want to do	Pearson Correlation	.701**	.712**	1	.554**	.538**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	206	206	206	206	206
There is accessing of broader target market with digital transformation.	Pearson Correlation	.558**	.546**	.554**	1	.433**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	206	206	206	206	206
Delivering value on a consistent basis as a result of digitalization	Pearson Correlation	.567**	.556**	.538**	.433**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	206	206	206	206	206

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 5, is the Pearson correlation matrix on Captivating digital content and potential market growth showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows $.433 < 712$. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 levels (2 tailed) and implies that Captivating digital content

had positive significant relationship with potential market growth ($r=.433 < 712$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .195$ with 879 degrees of freedom at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r.433 < 712 p>.05$).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise rejects the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed $r = .433 < 712$ is greater than the table value of $.195$, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we conclude that Captivating digital content had positive significant relationship with potential market growth as reported in the probability value of ($r= .433 < 712 p>.05$).

Discussions of Findings

Online Course Creators Had Positive Significant Relationship with Easy Access to Consumers

Hypotheses one showed that the computed $r = .396 < 750$ was greater than the table value of $.000$, Therefore, we conclude that online course creators had positive significant relationship with easy access to consumers as reported in the probability value of ($r= .396 < 750, p>.05$). Online learning can be beneficial because Students at their own pace can learn through online products. Virtual classrooms are available anywhere with an Internet connection, take advantage of this great way to travel. In support of these hypotheses Pallavi, Ramachandran and Chinnasamy, (2022) conducted an Empirical Study on Effectiveness of E-Learning Over Conventional Class Room Learning – A Case Study with Respect to Online Degree Programme in Higher Education. The development of online instruction programs for online course developers raises an interesting question. Online study designers follow the traditional methods or incorporate online programs' innovative approaches. Primary factors behind the use of online learning improve the quality of education, and also improve the cost-effectiveness of education by reducing costs. Face-to-face Online learning is used successfully with positive effects on career and education. A geographically distributed team within an organization can simultaneously train their skills through online sites and gain greater Competitiveness.

Captivating Digital Content Had Positive Significant Relationship with Potential Market Growth

Harting, Reichstein, Laemmle and Sprengel (2019) carried out a study on a Potentials of Digital Business Models in the retail industry – Empirical Results from European Experts. An elaborate business model is the fundament of every firm as it describes the manner of functioning. In the course of new developments through digitization, business models and processes have changed enormously and new business models are emerging like never before. The findings of the structural equation model analysis show that three determinants (Key Performance Indicators, Individualization and Efficiency) do have a positive as well as significant influence on the potentials of digital business models. Just the determinants Communication do have a negative as well as insignificant influence on the potentials of digital business models. In support of these literature, the result of hypotheses two revealed the computed $r = .433 < 712$ was greater than the table value of $.000$, Therefore, we conclude that Captivating digital content had positive significant relationship with potential market growth as reported in the probability value of ($r= .433 < 712 p>.05$).

Conclusion

The study concluded that online course creators and Captivating digital content had positive significant relationship with easy access to consumers and potential market growth. Entrepreneurship education is one of the knowledge transfer processes in creating entrepreneurs. The digital transformation in entrepreneurship education is a new approach and an important challenge in education to prepare students in the face of technological change. Digital innovation has demonstrated powers to complement, enrich and transform education, and has the potential to speed up progress towards Sustainable Development Goal for education and transform modes of provision of

universal access to learning. The advancement of digitalization brings significant changes in the business ecosystem across the globe, and helps businesses to develop beyond their internal market.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made by the study

- i. The institutions should try and create and launch online courses, to gain a better understanding of the target audience. To facilitate working directly with them through the quizzes, assignments, surveys, and feedback which then guide you toward what they need.
- ii. There is need to have captivating digital content to enable students to access the course material at any time of day or night, making it easier to fit learning into a busy schedule.

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